

AN ESTIMATION OF THE DEGREE OF CONTACT FOR THE SYSTEM OF
MONOSIZED SPHERICAL PARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

This article reports a new stereological method for the estimation of the degree of contact for a system of monosized spherical particles. Since this method is applicable to pointlike contacts, we can evaluate the degree of contact of ceramic particles in metal matrix composite in which the contact is assumed to be point. Our degree of contact is derived from the geometrical calculation of center-to-center distance between particles, evaluation of contact, and consideration of geometrical probability that two particles in contact are cut simultaneously by a test plane. In order to evaluate the reliability of our method, it is applied to a computer-simulated system of monosized spherical particles. The obtained degree of contact is consistent with that expected for the simulated system. Applying our method to a model material (Shirasu-balloon/aluminum alloy composite), we can well explain interrelations between the change in the degree of contact and some physical properties of the material.

KEYWORDS: Stereology/Quantitative Microscopy; Degree of Contact; Particulate Composite; Physical Property.

1. INTRODUCTION

In particle-dispersed composite, the degree of contact of dispersed particles can exert a significant influence on some properties such as tensile strength and electrical conductivity. There are some well-known methods to evaluate the degree of contact of grains or particles stereologically (1). Most of

those methods are concerned with the facial contact between the phase(s) of interest, however. Thus, they can not be applied to pointlike contacts between rigid particles such as ceramic particles in metal matrix composite, because two-dimensional observation on a test plane impossibly catch the three-dimensionally dispersed points each of which has no volume or area.

Recently, Robine et al. (2) reported a method to evaluate the number of pointlike contacts between monosized spherical particles. They introduced a concept of "biparticle", and found the "coordination number" (the number of contacts per particle) from a consideration on the "plane coordinance" which is defined as a function of the "euclidean distance" between particle sections on a test plane.

In this article we report an approach to estimate the degree of contact for the system of monosized spherical particles stereologically (by observing two-dimensional test section). The proposed method is based on a consideration on the geometrical probability, and has a potential to evaluate pointlike contacts more easily. We define the degree of contact as either the number of contacts per unit volume or the number of contacts per particle. With an appropriate modification, we apply this quantity to a Shirasu-balloon/aluminum alloy composite (SBAC) to examine the relationship between some physical properties of SBAC and the degree of contact of Shirasu-balloons.

2. DEGREE OF CONTACT FOR A SYSTEM OF MONOSIZED SPHERICAL PARTICLES

2.1 Estimation of contact from an observation of two-dimensional section As mentioned before, it is generally difficult to catch three-dimensionally dispersed points of contact by a two-dimensional section plane through material. If some assumptions are made, however, we can estimate such a contiguity from relatively straightforward geometrical analysis as follows:

First, we assume that the particles are spheres with the same radius of r_0 and are not deformed by contacting. Then we consider a two-dimensional test plane through the sample in which the particles assumed above are dispersed. On the test plane, circular features of various sizes are seen as in Fig. 1-a. Let the sectional radii and the coordinates of the centers of Circle i and j be r_i , r_j and (x_i, y_i) , (x_j, y_j) , respectively, then the

distances (z_i, z_j) of the centers of particles from the test plane are written as

$$z_i = (r_0^2 - r_i^2)^{1/2}; \quad z_j = (r_0^2 - r_j^2)^{1/2}. \quad (1)$$

As the particle center corresponding to each circular feature possibly exists either above or below the test plane (as C_i or C_i' in Fig. 1-b), there are two possible center-to-center distances (C_i-C_j or $C_i'-C_j$) between two particles. These two distances are written as

$$d^\pm = \{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2 + (z_i \mp z_j)^2\}^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where d^+ and d^- indicate the center-to-center distance between two particles whose centers are existing in the same side (C_i-C_j) and in each side ($C_i'-C_j$) of the test plane, respectively. It is apparent that d^+ is always smaller than d^- .

Now, we can know the probability c_{ij} of contact between the i -th and j -th particles by comparing $2r_0$ with d^\pm calculated from Eq. (2). The theoretical criteria for determining c_{ij} are summarized in Table 1. If two particles contact with each other, either d^+ or d^- equals $2r_0$. Converses seem to be not always true. In the case of $d^- = 2r_0$, the particles necessarily contact with each other, so $c_{ij} = 1$. In the case of $d^+ = 2r_0$, the situation is somewhat complex. If the centers of particles are in the same side to the test plane, they contact with each other. But if the centers of particles are in each side of the test plane, they do not contact. And the probability for the centers of particles to be in the same side to the test plane seems to be 0.5. The probability that two particles are in each side of the test plane and $d^+ = 2r_0$ is negligible, however, comparing with the probability that both particles are in the same side to the test plane and $d^+ = 2r_0$. Therefore, unity is assigned to c_{ij} when d^+ equals $2r_0$.

The theoretical criteria in Table 1 seems to be scarcely applicable to practical particles, because practical particles are not of the same size and truly spherical in a strict sense. So, it might be reasonable to assume a particle to be interpenetrated by another particle when d^+ or d^- is smaller than $2r_0$. This means that the volume of particle decreases by contacting, but such an assumption might well simulate practical contacting with some degree of local flattening or coalescence. Thus, we introduce a new assignment for practical c_{ij} as in Table 2. In these

criteria, 0.5 is assigned to c_{ij} when $2r_0$ is between d^+ and d^- , because in this case, the probability for the centers of both particles to be in the same side to the test plane is considered to be 0.5.

Using the criteria of Table 1 or Table 2, we can assign the degree of contact, c_{ij} , for any pair of particles, and thus obtain the total number of contacts C_T by summing up the degree of contact of all possible pairs of particles as

$$C_T = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N c_{ij} \quad (3)$$

where N is the number of particles observed on the test plane.

Next we examine the spatial range within which the contacts are estimated with the above method. As shown in Fig. 2, the particles which are observed on a test plane must have their centers not farther than r_0 from the test plane. Therefore, the contacts estimated with the above method must also occur within the distance r_0 from the test plane. But it is noted that all the contacts within this $2r_0$ range can not be estimated. Such an example is also shown schematically in Fig. 2. While the contact point A is derived from the two particles observed on the test plane, the point B comes from the contact of one particle observed and another not observed on the test plane.

Then, we have to introduce the probability of the detectable contact occurrence in order to estimate the total number of contacts occurring within the distance r_0 from the test plane.

2.2 Probability of the detectable contact occurrence In order to obtain the probability P of the detectable contact occurrence, we must consider the following two kinds of probabilities: (1) the probability P_1 for a contact to occur within the distance r_0 from the test plane, and (2) the probability P_2 for such a contact to be detected from the section of the particles (*i.e.* the probability for both Particles i and j to be cut by the test plane simultaneously). Suppose that Particle j is in contact with Particle i , the center of Particle j is on the spherical surface radius of which is $2r_0$ and center coincides with that of Particle i . And probabilities P_1 and P_2 vary depending on the distance z_i of the center of Particle i from the test plane (Fig. 3). Because of the symmetry of configura-

tion, it is enough to consider the center of Particle i below the test plane only.

Consulting to Fig. 3, the probabilities P_1 and P_2 are seen to be expressed as the ratio of the surface area generated from rotating the arc j_0j_3 (the total of dotted and bold curves) and arc j_1j_2 (bold curve only) around the z -axis, respectively, to the surface area of sphere with radius of $2r_0$. Now let us consider the situation shown in Fig. 3-c and define angles ϕ_0 , ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 as in the figure, the surface areas S_1 , S_2 corresponding to P_1 and P_2 , respectively, and S_T of the sphere of radius $2r_0$ are

$$S_1 = 8\pi r_0^2 \int_{\phi_0}^{\pi} \sin\theta d\theta = 8\pi r_0^2 (1 + \cos\phi_0), \quad (4)$$

$$S_2 = \begin{cases} 8\pi r_0^2 \int_{\phi_1}^{\phi_2} \sin\theta d\theta = 8\pi r_0^2 (\cos\phi_1 - \cos\phi_2) & (0 \leq z_i < r_0) \\ 0 & (r_0 \leq z_i \leq 2r_0), \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$S_T = 4\pi(2r_0)^2 = 16\pi r_0^2. \quad (6)$$

And from the definitions,

$$\cos\phi_0 = \frac{(r_0 - z_i)}{r_0}; \quad \cos\phi_1 = \frac{(r_0 - z_i)}{2r_0}; \quad \cos\phi_2 = \frac{-(r_0 + z_i)}{2r_0}. \quad (7)$$

Putting Eq. (7) into Eqs. (4) and (5) and dividing them by Eq. (6), we obtain the probabilities P_1 and P_2 as

$$P_1 = \frac{8\pi r_0(2r_0 - z_i)}{16\pi r_0^2} = 1 - \frac{z_i}{2r_0}, \quad (8)$$

$$P_2 = \begin{cases} \frac{8\pi r_0^2}{16\pi r_0^2} = \frac{1}{2} & (0 \leq z_i < r_0) \\ 0 & (r_0 \leq z_i \leq 2r_0). \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Since z_i is expected to be distributed uniformly from 0 to $2r_0$, the probability P of the detectable contact occurrence is derived from P_1 and P_2 as

$$P = \frac{\int_0^{2r_0} P_2 dz_i}{\int_0^{2r_0} P_1 dz_i} = \frac{r_0/2}{r_0} = \frac{1}{2} \quad (10)$$

According to the consideration above, we can estimate the real number of contacts within the distance r_0 from the test plane by dividing C_T by P ($= 0.5$).

Now we can express the degree of contact as follows:

(1) The number of contacts per unit volume (C_V) is

$$C_V = \frac{C_T}{2r_0AP} \quad (11)$$

where A is the total test area on the section plane.

(2) The number of contacts per particle (C_N) is

$$C_N = \frac{2C_V}{N_V} = \frac{4C_V r_0 A}{N} = \frac{2C_T}{NP} \quad (12)$$

where N is the total number of particles observed within the test plane and N_V is the number of particles per unit volume.

3. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

3.1 Experimental procedure In order to examine the reliability of the proposed method, it was applied for estimating the degree of contact of computer-simulated system of monosized spherical particles. Particles of radius 20 (arbitrary unit) were dispersed at random in 552x552x552 space. If particles overlapped each other, the later-generated particle was moved to be just in contact with the former. The volume fractions of particles were controlled to be 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40 and 45 vol. %, and for each volume fraction 10 different samples were generated using different series of random numbers. After cutting off the margin of 20 thick, 8 test planes were cut from each sample and the degree of contact of dispersed particles was determined from the observation of these test planes using the proposed method. The obtained degrees of contact were averaged for each volume fraction.

3.2 Results Figs. 4-a and 4-b show the relation between the estimated degrees of contact per particle (C_N^* and C_N^{**} derived from c_{ij} s according to Tables 1 and 2, respectively) and virtual ones (C_N^0). As seen in Fig. 4-a, the estimated degree of contact C_N^* from the theoretical criteria in Table 1 well coincides with the virtual degree of contact C_N^0 of the simulated system. On the other hand, the estimated degree of contact C_N^{**} from practical criteria in Table 2 is slightly smaller than C_N^0 , especially at lower volume fractions (i.e. lower C_N s; Fig. 4-b). The discrepancy between C_N^{**} and C_N^0 is rather small, however, and C_N^{**} agrees with C_N^0 at larger volume fractions. On the basis of the results above, we will use the criteria in Table 2 for obtaining c_{ij} s of practical material.

4. Applications

We tried to apply the proposed method to evaluate the degree of contact of Shirasu-balloons (SB) in Shirasu-balloon/aluminum alloy composites (SBAC). SB are hollow microballoons made from volcanic ash called "Shirasu". SBAC were prepared by a pressure casting technique. The preparation condition of SBAC is summarized in Table 3. There are two problems which might be unfavorable to the direct application of the proposed method to practical materials, however.

First, the shape of practical particles is not truly spherical while the proposed method assumes particles strictly spherical. Therefore, the proposed method may be applied to practical systems only when the particles are approximately spherical. In such a case, the equivalent area diameter $(2(A_i/\pi))^{1/2}$, where A_i is the sectional area of the particle) and the gravity center should be used instead of geometrical diameter and geometrical center of the particle. We examined the roundness $(4\pi A_i/P_i^2)$, where P_i is the perimeter length of the section of particle) of SB on the test plane of SBAC by digital image analyzer. The average and the standard deviation of the roundness of SB were 0.84 and 0.11, respectively. It is known that the roundness of circle measures about 0.90 by digital image analyzer (3), so that SB can well be approximated to spheres.

Second, a system of particles usually have a size distribution. The proposed method is exclusively dealing with a system of monosized spherical particles. Therefore, it may not be applicable to polydispersed system of particles in a strict sense. According to the principle for the evaluation of the degree of contact proposed here, however, the existence of smaller particles tends to increase the estimated number of contacts while the larger particles have a tendency to decrease it. Thus, the both effects might work to cancel out each other. On the basis of the consideration above, the obtained degree of contact would not be different so much from the real degree of contact of the system if we adopt the mean diameter as a representative diameter of polydispersed particles. The size distribution of SB was calculated from the measured equivalent area diameters of SB by Schwartz-Saltykov's method (4). The mean diameter of SB and the standard deviation were 0.159 mm and 0.053mm, respectively. We use this mean diameter as the representative diameter of SB.

Ten test areas (1.20 mm x 1.28 mm each) were selected at random from each test plane, and processed by digital image analyzer to measure the equivalent area diameter and the gravity center of each image of particle. The degrees of contact of SB were first calculated for each test area, and were averaged for each specimen later. The obtained C_V^{**} and C_N^{**} (** indicates that these are obtained from the criteria in Table 2) are shown with the volume fraction of SB in Fig. 5-a and 5-b. It is noticed that both C_V^{**} and C_N^{**} increase linearly with the volume fraction of SB in these figures, but beyond 50 % of SB the degree of contact increases at higher rate. This behavior is consistent with the changes in some physical properties of SBAC shown in Fig. 6: tensile strength (Fig. 6-a) and electrical conductivity (Fig. 6-b). It is no doubt that tensile strength and electrical conductivity of SBAC decrease with increasing SB, because SB do harm to these properties. The volume fraction can not explain the drastic change in property at around 50 % SB, but the degree of contact can. Therefore, it can be said that the degree of contact must be one of the parameters which play important roles on the properties of metal-matrix composite.

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Table 1. Theoretical criteria for determining the probability c_{ij} of contact between two particles.

Condition	c_{ij}
$d^- \geq d^+ > 2r_0$	0
$d^- > d^+ = 2r_0$	1.0
$d^- > 2r_0 > d^+$	0
$2r_0 \geq d^- \geq d^+$	1.0

Table 2. A practical criteria for determining c_{ij} .

Condition	c_{ij}
$d^- \geq d^+ \geq 2r_0$	0
$d^- > 2r_0 \geq d^+$	0.5
$2r_0 \geq d^- \geq d^+$	1.0

Fig. 2. Profile view of particles cut normal to a test plane (TP) and through the center of each particle.

Fig. 1. a) Particles observed on a test plane, and b) their profile view which is normal to the test plane.

Fig. 3. Figures showing section through both centers of contacting particles i and j and normal to the test plane (TP). Surface areas S_1 and S_2 (generated by rotating arcs j_0j_2 and j_1j_3 around the z-axis) corresponding to probabilities P_1 and P_2 change with z_i .

Fig. 4. Relationship between estimated (C_N^* and C_N^{**}) and virtual (C_N^0) degree of contact for the simulated system of monosized spherical particles.

Table 3. Preparation condition of SBAC.

Matrix alloy	Al-12%Si
Size of SB (mm)	0.149 - 0.210
Vol. % of SB in SBAC	0 - 60
Preform preheat (K)	723
Casting temperature (K)	973
Casting pressure (MPa)	6.5

Fig. 5. Relationship between the degree of contact (C_V^{**} or C_N^{**}) and volume fraction (V_V) of SB in SBAC. a) C_V^{**} vs. V_V . b) C_N^{**} vs. V_V .

Fig. 6. Representative physical properties of SBAC in terms of V_V of SB. a) tensile strength, and b) electrical conductivity.